

An Analysis of key Growth Drivers and Challenges in Organised Sector of Indian Retail Industry

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ABSTRACT

The Indian retail industry is considered as one among the most vibrant industries in country and one of the pillars of economy. The Indian retail industry is also one among the most contributing sectors to GDP (Gross domestic product) and employment of the country. The Indian retail industry especially organised sector has witnessed an exponential growth in last few years, at the same time faced some challenges. In this article, a modest attempt is made to critically analyse key drivers of exponential growth of organised sector of Indian retail industry, as well as key challenges faced. The article is based on exploratory research and secondary data. The data was accumulated from books, journals, magazines, websites and other published sources available. This article provides an original insight of key growth drivers and challenges in organised sector of Indian retail industry.

KEYWORDS: Growth drivers, Challenges, Retail market, Retail industry, India.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 An overview of Indian retail industry

The Indian retail industry is one among the most contributing sectors to Indian GDP at the rate of 14 to 15% (Dikshit, 2011) and 8% in the employment of the country (FICCI, 2011). The Indian retail industry is considered as one among the most vibrant industries in India and one of the pillars of Indian economy. A bright future of the Indian retail sector can be glanced with the growth estimation of this sector, as India is estimated as the fastest growing retail market and will become one of the top five retail markets in the worlds in terms of economic value (Majumder, 2011). In 2011, from the perspective of investment in the retail sector, India has been ranked in Global Retail Development Index as 4th most attractive country among the 30 flourishing market around the globe (FICCI, 2011).

Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) 2014 of the US Based global management consulting firm A T Kearney ranked the Indian retail industry at 20th position among the top 30 developing countries. *Figure 1* explains the competitive position of India in comparison to other 30 promising countries of the world. Moriarty *et al.* (2014) explain that in GRDI 2014, India has been dropped in 20th place from its 14th place in 2013 due to slow economic growth (4.7% only), currency fluctuations, high rate of consumer price inflation, government debt, high current account deficits and strict FDI policies.

But, Moriarty *et al.* (2014) mention further that India is still an eye-catching long-term retail destination due to several reasons, which are the population of 1.2 billion, younger population (50% of the total population is under 30 years), one-third of the total population is cities resident, increasing disposable income and pro-business policies attitude of the current National Democratic Alliance (NDA) government headed by the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) and prime minister Mr. Narendra Modi. Many industry experts have positive feelings for long-term GDP outlook and industrial growth of India. According to Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) 2014, despite the several slumps,

Indian retailing sector has a potential to grow in the future and the market is attractive for investment. Figure 2 explains the attractiveness in terms of investment in Indian Retail Sector as to consider.

■ On the radar
 ■ To consider
 ■ Lower priority

2014 rank	Country	Market attractiveness (25%)	Country risk (25%)	Market saturation (25%)	Time pressure (25%)	GRDI score	Change in rank compared to 2013
1	Chile	100.0	100.0	13.2	47.3	65.1	+1
2	China	60.9	52.5	44.5	100.0	64.4	+2
3	Uruguay	93.4	57.5	70.3	32.4	63.4	—
4	United Arab Emirates	98.5	82.3	17.5	43.8	60.5	+1
5	Brazil	99.4	59.8	48.7	33.2	60.3	-4
6	Armenia	26.4	35.3	81.5	86.7	57.5	+4
7	Georgia	32.4	32.8	79.6	78.8	55.9	+1
8	Kuwait	78.8	72.6	32.9	31.7	54.0	+1
9	Malaysia	66.7	68.7	32.2	43.5	52.8	+4
10	Kazakhstan	45.4	38.5	72.7	54.3	52.7	+1
11	Turkey	83.6	50.2	46.5	30.2	52.6	-5
12	Russia	94.0	38.4	30.7	46.4	52.4	+11
13	Peru	46.0	43.0	61.9	51.3	50.6	-1
14	Panama	56.2	46.9	52.7	41.3	49.3	+8
15	Indonesia	46.2	33.4	57.7	59.6	49.2	+4
16	Saudi Arabia	72.3	67.3	29.5	27.4	49.1	—
17	Oman	75.1	79.1	27.0	11.1	48.1	—
18	Sri Lanka	6.3	36.7	78.8	67.3	47.3	-3
19	Nigeria	39.6	6.6	92.3	48.0	46.6	N/A
20	India	26.4	39.0	72.3	43.4	45.3	-6
21	Colombia	50.6	43.0	53.5	29.4	44.2	-3
22	Jordan	49.8	43.7	65.6	15.2	43.6	-2
23	Philippines	33.0	33.2	55.8	50.5	43.1	N/A
24	Costa Rica	62.1	45.9	40.4	21.5	42.5	N/A
25	Mexico	80.0	54.4	2.9	31.8	42.3	-4
26	Botswana	26.1	60.7	34.8	44.1	41.4	-1
27	Morocco	24.1	35.5	69.5	35.7	41.2	—
28	Vietnam	3.8	21.9	75.0	55.7	39.1	N/A
29	Namibia	8.6	57.9	27.2	58.8	38.1	-3
30	Azerbaijan	22.0	29.5	82.3	18.6	38.1	-1

0 = low attractiveness

100 = high attractiveness

0 = high risk
100 = low risk

0 = saturated
100 = not saturated

0 = no time pressure
100 = urgency to enter

Figure 1: Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) 2014
Source: Adopted from Moriarty et al. (2014)

Figure 2: Global Retail Development Index 2014: Market attractiveness
 Source: Adopted from Moriarty *et al.* (2014)

1.2. Organised retailing in India

The retail sector of India, especially organised retailing is passing through the transformation from last one decade and despite the several slump, the organised retail market is growing exponentially. The organised retail segment is shifting towards the adoption of modern retailing concepts. In 2007, the Indian retail market size was approximated at USD 339.7 billion; in which USD 13.9 billion was organised retail market size. In 2010, the Indian retail market size was approximated at USD 435 billion, in which 95% market (USD 414) was of an unorganised traditional retail market and only 5% i.e. USD 21 billion was organised retail market size (FICCI, 2011). In 2011-12, the Indian retail market was taped at USD 500 billion in which the organised retail market has been just 7%. The Indian retail market is anticipated to reach USD 738.71 billion by 2016-17 with a compounded growth rate of 15% per annum. While, the organised retail is anticipated to attain the 10.2% share of the total retail market with a growth rate of 24% (The Hindu, 2014). In 2014, the Indian retail market was estimated at USD 490 billion and was projected to reach USD 865 billion by 2023 with a compounded annual growth rate of 6% (The Hindu Business Line, 2014). The *figure 3* indicates that in 2013, the organised retail market was 8% and expected to grow 24% by 2020.

Figure 3: Significant scope for expansion in organised retail
 Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

Table 1.1 depicts the comparative situation of organised and unorganised retailing sector of India and other countries of the world.

Country	Organised	Unorganised
USA	85	15
Taiwan	81	19
Malaysia	55	45
Indonesia	30	70
China	20	80
India	08	92

Source: Adopted from (Madaan, 2012)

The growth of the organised retail sector in India can also be glanced in terms of sheer space. In 2012, the total organised retail space supply was 2.5 million square feet, which was increased by 4.7 million square feet with a growth rate of 78% (Chakraborty, 2013).

The Secretary General of Assocham, India D. S. Rawat, also glanced a phenomenal growth of the Indian retail sector and said that “favourable demographics, increasing urbanisation, an increase in the number of nuclear families, increasing affluence amid buyers, increasing attraction and preference for branded products and greater aspirations are the factors that will enhance the Indian retail consumption” (The Economic Times, 2014).

1.3. India’s retail market

The consumer market in India is getting a robust growth and the consumption level in India is assumed to be double in the next five years from 750 billion USD to 1.5 trillion USD. According to panel members of 7th Food and Grocery Forum of India, the food and grocery retail market of India has ample growth opportunities and that segment of the retail market constitutes about 60% of the total retail market (Phulia and Sharma, 2014; Moriarty et al., 2013). *Figure 4* explains the breakup of USD 500 billion retail sector of India.

Figure 4: India’s retail market
Source: Adopted from Moriarty et al. (2013)

The growing number of middle-class households is also a contributing factor to the growth of the Indian retail sector. It has been estimated that 91 million households will be in the category of the middle-class from its 21 million by 2030. It has also been estimated that 570 million people will

prefer to live in the cities in 2030 (Chakraborty, 2013; FICCI, 2011). The growing middle class is redefining the luxury market with their changing buying habits. The growth of retailing sector can also be glanced from the fact that about 40% of the luxury goods sales in India occur from the non-metros customers (Rai and Gopal, 2014). The huge population, especially the young population, higher domestic consumption and the favourable macro trends are other contributing factors to the exponential growth of the Indian retail sector.

2. OBJECTIVES

In this article, an attempt is made:

- To critically analyse key drivers of exponential growth of organised sector of Indian retail industry.
- To critically analyse key challenges faced by organised sector of Indian retail industry.

3. METHODOLOGY

The article is based on exploratory research and secondary data. The data was accumulated from books, journals, magazines, websites and other published sources available. This article provides an original insight of key growth drivers and challenges in Indian retail industry.

4. KEY DRIVERS TO THE EXPONENTIAL GROWTH OF ORGANISED SECTOR OF THE INDIAN RETAIL INDUSTRY

- **The huge population, especially the younger population:** India is considered as one among the largest emerging markets of the world due to its population, which is over 1.2 billion (Rahman, 2012). India is also considered as one of the largest economies in terms of purchasing power of the population. The 50% of the total Indian population is below the age of 30 years and about 1/3 of the Indian population resides in cities (Rai and Gopal, 2014). Table 2 presents the percentage of population below the age of 25 years in different countries.

Country	Percentage of Population
India	53
China	42
Indonesia	30
USA	30
Japan	27
Germany	26
Source: Adopted from (Madaan, 2012)	

- **Changing lifestyle and consumer behaviour:** Due to increasing working population, comfortable life style, more travel and leisure are the preferences of Indian customers. These factors are the drivers for the growth of retailing in India; whether it is Appliances, Cosmetics & Toiletries, Electronics etc. (Handa and Grover, 2012).
- **Rising affluence amid consumers:** It is estimated that 91 million households will be in the category of the middle-class from its 21 million by 2030 (Chakraborty, 2013; FICCI, 2011). This increase in the middle-class households is a contributing factor towards the growth of the retail sector.
- **Demographic changes and improvements in the standard of living:** The growing middle class is redefining the luxury market with their changing buying habits. The growth of retailing sector can also be glanced from the fact that about 40% of the luxury goods sales in India occur from the non-metros customers (Rai and Gopal, 2014).
- **Favourable demographics:** The Demography Dynamics are also favourable for the Indian organised retail sector as approximately 60% of Indian population is young and below the age of 30 years (Rahman, 2012).
- **Changing consumer preferences and shopping habits:** Shopping behaviour of consumers has been totally changed due to the change in taste and preferences of consumers. Due to the online retailing consumers are well aware of new brands and stores and they buy according to their needs and occasions. Consumers are driving the growth of organised retail. Therefore, the organised retailing is not only growing its market, but also compelling the retailers to offer a wider range of brands as well as a variety (D&B, 2014).

- **The increase in a working population:** India is the second largest country in the world in terms of population after China. And, it is the largest consumer market in the world due to its favourable demographics (D&B, 2014). An increase in the number of working women has increased the growth of discretionary items. There has been a 20% increase in the number of working women population in the last decade.
- **The emergence of nuclear families:** With the passage of time there is a shift from joint families to nuclear families. The income level of nuclear families has been increased because both the members have started to earn; which results in an increase in purchasing power and lack of time. Thereby nuclear families are expecting everything under one roof. This led to the development of organised retailing.
- **Increasing urbanisation:** The preference shift of population towards the urban livings is also a good sign of the growth of the Indian organised retail sector. It is estimated that 570 million people will prefer to live in the cities in 2030 (Chakraborty, 2013; FICCI, 2011).
- **The increase in disposable income and customer aspiration:** Booming Indian economy is a consequential source of opportunity for the retailing sector. India is the third largest country of the world in terms of purchasing power of consumers (Rahman, 2012). Due to large working population and an increase in double-income households, the disposable income, as well as the purchasing power of consumers, especially in urban India, has been growing. The growing preference for branded products and services, higher aspirations, demand and increase in the expenditure for luxury items are the major cause of the growth of this sector in India. The branded products, especially in the categories of Cosmetics, Apparels, Shoes, Watches, Beverages, Food and even Jewellery are being preferred as the lifestyle products by the urban consumers of India.
- **Increase in per capita income:** The per capita income of Indian consumers is ₹ 44,345 (Rahman, 2012), which is growing and can be referred from *figure 5*. Due to an increase in per capita income, the household consumption is increasing, which is a good sign for organised retailers. As the earnings are increasing, a proportionate increase in spending can also be glanced. Moreover, the Indian economy is expected to grow by a rate of 8% and salaries are also expected to hike with a rate of 15% (Rahman, 2012). This in turn will increase the household consumption, which is a healthy sign for manufacturers and retailers of consumer goods and services.

Figure 5: Rising per capita income in India
Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- **Increasing use of plastic money:** Among the Indian consumers, the use of plastic money has been increased and due to this the consumers prefer to buy the merchandise in the category of Apparel, Consumer Durable Goods, Food and Grocery etc.
- **Improvements in infrastructure and enhanced availability of retail space:** Due to the overall betterment of transportation infrastructure and services in India, now the consumers are able to cover a distance to reach a particular retail outlet. *Figure 6* depicts the enhanced availability of retail space and mall space breakup in India.

Figure 6: Mall space breakup in India

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- Easy credit availability:** Ease in getting credit cards and ease of use of credit cards for shopping has also boosted the growth of the organised retail sector. Due to the issuance of credit cards at a larger piece by Foreign and Indian banks has increased the retail growth. According to the RBI, as of the financial year 2009, the total number of outstanding credit and debit cards in India was 24.7 million and 137.4 million respectively (D&B, 2014).
- Growing liberalisation of the FDI policy in the past decade:** *Figure 7* states the Growing liberalisation of the FDI policy in India. The main benefit of FDI is that it is both supplementary and complimentary with regards to local investment. Due to FDI companies has gained access to world class technology and supplementary funds. Companies have also access to new management practices around the world and get the chance to become the part of a global market system (Prasad and Harikumar, 2013). With the help of FDI, companies will get new technologies and skills from other countries; which results in infrastructure development of the nation. It will also lead to help in creating more value for money for the customers.

Figure 7: Favourable FDI policy encouraging investment

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- Organised retail concentration in tier II and III cities:** Retail revolution started with the tier I cities in India, which thereby has been saturated (D&B, 2014). Now retailers are focusing on tier II and tier III cities as depicted in *figure 8*. Due to the changing landscape of Indian retail segment and the increase in competition has forced the retailers to find out the growth opportunities in tier II and III cities.

Figure 8: Organised retail in India
 Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- The internet drives awareness and online purchases:** There has been a huge increase in the number of internet users and online buyers in India (D&B, 2014). Online retailing has been increased due to increase in awareness of the internet and online buying; which has opened a whole new channel of retailing in the Indian retail scenario. Online retailing is prevalent due to ease in buying and ease in getting the goods on the doorstep.
- Experimentation with formats:** Due to huge competition in retailing market of India the retailers are experimenting with the new formats (Handa and Grover, 2012).
- Store design:** Shopping malls and supermarkets are growing day by day, which leads to improvements in infrastructure. Large availability of retail space & competition has also encouraged the retailers to adopt attractive store designs and make the ambience eye-catching (Handa and Grover, 2012). This results in more visits to the shopping malls which ultimately lead to more sales & higher growth of organised retail in India.
- Brief about growth value propositions:** *Figure 9* summarises the major growth value propositions in this Indian retail sector. Which can be described as higher brand consciousness, growing aspiration levels of consumers and appetite to experiment, growing young population and working women, rising incomes and purchasing power, credit availability, changing consumer preference and growing urbanisation, rapid real estate and infrastructure development, emergence of new categories, development of supply chains and improving their efficiency, easy availability of credit to suppliers, expansion of existing players, R&D, innovation and new product development etc.

Figure 9: Growth value proposition in organised retail industry
 Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

5. KEY CHALLENGES IN ORGANISED SECTOR OF INDIAN RETAIL INDUSTRY

- **Porter’s Five Forces analysis of the organised retail sector:** *Figure 10* explains the five forces of competition in the retail industry of India.

Figure 10: Porter’s Five Forces analysis of organised retail sector
 Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- **Shortage of skilled/trained manpower:** 75 to 80% of the total manpower is required for store operations in the organised retail industry and front/end line assistant profiles are major positions for employment opportunities in the sector (FICCI, 2011). Unfortunately, in India, very few retail operations specific courses are offered at graduate and post graduate level. Moreover, there is also a shortage of niche retail operations specific courses in the area of store merchandising, supply chain management in retailing, CRM in retailing, stock management, customer service management etc.
- **Lack of industry status:** The retail industry in India is still fighting for the industry status from the government. In the absence of this industry status, the organised retailing is facing issues in procuring the required finance and fiscal benefits.
- **Policy-induced barriers:** There a time’s need that Indian government should establish an apex body for governing all the retail operation in India, as the organised retail sector is administrated by two different ministries of the government of India. The Ministries of Commerce formulates policies pertained to retail operations in India, while the Ministry of Consumer Affairs takes care of licensing and other legislation related to retailing. A single apex body can govern retail operations and address the grievances of retailers more effectively.
- **Real estate market:** The real estate market is offering the retail space with high prices and low availability. A brief comparison of rent as %age of sales to Indian retailers and international retailers has been presented in *table 3*. It is very difficult to find appropriate space in a central location of the cities due to an absence of retail space planning in India. Moreover, space which is available for use can easily be interchanged for commercial utilisation. Other reasons for retail space issues are infrequent auctioning of government owned lands, litigation disputes of land owners and fragmented private holdings.

Table 3: A comparison of rent as %age of sales		
Format	Indian Retailers	International Retailers
Hyper market	5-10%	1-5%
Speciality retailers	15-30%	10-12%

Source: Adopted from (Madaan, 2012)

- **Government regulations:** Government regulations, especially the Urban Land Ceiling Act) for the development of real estate is hindering the growth of the retail sector. The existing labour laws are restricting the retailers for offering a 24/7 shopping experience to their customers. Moreover, the multi-stage taxation system and other taxation laws are hindering the growth of this sector.
- **Technology:** Technology is a major challenge faced by organised retailers for effective management of retail operations. First of all, the technology available in India in this sector is out-dated. A strong need of latest technology (digital merchandising, online inventory monitoring system, mobile payment, etc.) is there to cope up with the customer aspirations.
- **Lack of efficient supply-chain management and distribution channel:** Distribution channels are an integral part of the retail industry. The main role of the distribution channels is to deliver the right kind of goods at the right place at the right time. The improper infrastructure and distribution channels are the reasons for inefficient distribution processes in India. Moreover, supply chains are expensive in India. Therefore, the stakeholders in the retail industry are required to improvise distribution channels as well as supply chain systems, so that they can meet the desired quality and service level by their customers.
- **Understanding customers:** Understanding customer behaviour is not an easy business. However, converting your customers into loyal customers is a more critical task in the retail industry. Retailers are required to have the implementation of effective CRM as well as a loyalty programme.
- **Inefficient power supply:** Organised retail outlets utilise the electricity for various store management orations like billing systems, cold storing, lighting, lifts, escalators, air conditioning etc. and need large volumes of electricity for the same. Due to inefficient and insufficient power supply, retailers have to invest for ensuring power backups.
- **Competition from unorganised sector:** Competition from the unorganised sector is also a challenge confronted by organised retailers in India as unorganised retailers caters niche and more personalised service to their customers.
- **The slow growth of organised retail market:** The people are shifting continuously to modern stores from their preferred traditional stores. But this organised (modern) retail format could account only for 8% of the total retail market (Moriarty *et al.* (2014), which is a challenge for stakeholders.
- **Online retailing:** Moriarty *et al.* (2014) estimated that e-commerce market in India will grow more that 50% in the coming five years. This may be a big challenge to store based organised retailers. *Figure 11* presents a comparison of total retail sales and e-commerce sales. The applications of internet among the young population of India are increasing day by day and speed of the internet as well. Cash on the delivery option by online retailers is a key factor for the growth. However, the inventory management, resource availability and logistic planning are important challenges for the growth of online retailing in India.

Figure 11: Comparison of total retail & retail e-commerce sale in India
Source: Adopted from (Mahajan, 2015)

- **Other bottlenecks:** Few other bottlenecks of Indian Retail are as follows: there is a long way to meet international standards by Indian organised retailers. There is a lack of required retail space for organised retailing and there is no fixed consumption pattern. Other bottlenecks are inadequate utilities, IT infrastructure hurdles, policy-related hurdles, limited consumer insights, taxation challenges.

6. CONCLUSION

The Indian retail industry has witnessed an exponential growth in last few years, at the same time faced some challenges. Key drivers to the exponential growth of the Indian retail industry are the huge population, especially the younger population, changing lifestyle and consumer behavior, rising affluence amid consumers, demographic changes and improvements in the standard of living, favourable demographics, changing consumer preferences and shopping habits, the increase in a working population, the emergence of nuclear families, increasing urbanization, the increase in disposable income and customer aspiration, increase in per capita income, increasing use of plastic money, improvements in infrastructure and enhanced availability of retail space, easy credit availability, growing liberalisation of the FDI policy in the past decade, organised retail concentration in tier II and III cities, the internet drives awareness and online purchases, experimentation with formats, store design, brief about growth value propositions, higher brand consciousness, growing aspiration levels of consumers and appetite to excrement, growing young population and working women, rising incomes and purchasing power, credit availability, changing consumer preference and growing urbanisation, rapid real estate and infrastructure development, emergence of new categories, development of supply chains and improving their efficiency, easy availability of credit to suppliers, expansion of existing players, R&D, innovation and new product development etc.

Key challenges in Indian retail industry are shortage of skilled/trained manpower, lack of industry status, policy-induced barriers, real estate market, government regulations, technology, lack of efficient supply-chain management and distribution channel, understanding customers, inefficient power supply, competition from unorganised sector, the slow growth of organised retail market, online retailing and other bottlenecks like there is a long way to meet international standards by Indian organised retailers, there is a lack of required retail space for organised retailing and there is no fixed consumption pattern, inadequate utilities, IT infrastructure hurdles, policy-related hurdles, limited consumer insights and taxation challenges etc.

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